

Migrant
Integration through
Locally designed
Experiences

LEVERAGING EU RESOURCES TO PROMOTE MIGRANTS' POLITICAL INCLUSION

HOW TO BUILD SUSTAINABLE, MULTI-STAKEHOLDER AND INCLUSIVE NETWORKS

MILE POLICY BRIEF 3

APRIL 2023

AUTHORS: AMANDINE DESILLE, DAVIDE GNES

AND BEATRICE TOMMASI ON BEHALF OF INTEGRIM LAB

SUPPORTED BY EVA KASPEROVA, CREME (ASTON UNIVERSITY) AND
MARIA GRAZIA MONTELLA, INTEGRIM LAB

Co-funded by
the European Union

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Migrants participate in the economy of the hosting countries, but to a lesser extent in their political life. This policy brief explores the reasons behind this and the way in which, through the use of EU-funded projects and the participation in EU-wide networks, municipalities create conditions for migrant individuals and communities to participate in the public debate and decision-making as political actors and agents of change.

More specifically, the brief explores the potential of EU resources to foster migrant political inclusion at municipal level across Europe. Drawing on the five reports published as part of the [MILE project](#) and wider literature, this brief describes the challenges and opportunities linked to such resources. First, we provide a general **overview of existing EU-level financial resources and networks** that municipalities should consider. Second, drawing on examples of best practice in this field, we outline a few **recommendations for municipalities** willing to foster migrant political inclusion.

Why are EU funding schemes relevant for municipalities? EU funding can support municipalities in achieving the goal of migrant political inclusion. However, evidence from the four municipalities involved in the MILE project suggests that European municipalities have so far invested limited European and national resources in supporting migrant political inclusion.

Indeed, stable sources of funding, such as municipal budgets and national money transfers, are traditionally allocated to policy areas perceived as more salient, from mainstreamed social and civic programmes for all citizens to migrant-oriented integration activities such as language classes or vocational training.

While EU funds can lead to structural dependency and short-term vision and planning, they have several advantages:

1. The structure of EU-funded projects makes it possible to design them as **pilot projects** to address issues in innovative ways.
2. They encourage a **multi-stakeholder approach**, which may then facilitate the inclusion of migrant residents.
3. They promote the creation of **durable networks of people, institutions, and other organisations**, favouring exchange of good practices and fostering a municipality's reputational standing at national and international level.

Therefore, EU funding opportunities can enhance the long-term sustainability of such activities. Overall, EU projects provide municipalities with the unique opportunity to include migrant individuals, organisations and communities as project partners from the start, paving the way for the creation of sustainable inclusive mechanisms for migrants' political inclusion.

1 CURRENT USE OF EU FUNDING SCHEMES AND PROJECTS ON MIGRANT POLITICAL INCLUSION

Overall, the findings¹ show the existence of a very limited range of activities and projects on political inclusion of migrant communities in the examined municipalities. On the one hand, the vast majority of projects and activities targeting the migrant population concern social, economic and cultural inclusion (e.g. language courses, vocational training, inter-cultural dialogue). On the other hand, existing activities and funding opportunities directed to the city population at large (e.g. participatory budgets) hold the potential of fostering political inclusion of more vulnerable segments of the residents, including migrants, yet they are not levered for these groups.

Notably, in recent years, the cities of Birmingham and Ioannina have implemented activities that specifically focus on migrants’ political participation with promising developments, although some critical elements also need to be underlined.

Birmingham

In Birmingham, the EU-funded ‘Mi-Friendly Cities’ project² on promoting ‘active citizenship’ of migrants was followed up by ‘Foundation for Integration’, an AMIF-funded project³ that supported local migrant organisations and the set-up of the Migrant Advice Portal, an online advisory platform for migrants. Besides their content, these projects have allowed the municipality to **hire dedicated staff** and **establish links with migrant and refugee organisations** for joint activities with several other partners. These connections proved to be the stepping stone to the MILE project and the creation of a **consultative body involving migrant residents**.

It is also clear that political inclusion is promoted primarily through EU funding.

1) This section builds on the five reports elaborated during the first phase of the MILE project (2023), including: Eva Kašperová, Monder Ram, & Heila Sha. (2023). *The inclusion of migrants in policy making. A report on Birmingham, United Kingdom.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941479>; George Kadylis, Iris Polyzou, Katerina Vezyrgianni, Stavros Spyrellis, & Pavlos Baltas. (2023). *The inclusion of migrants in policy making. A report on Ioannina, Greece.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941608>; Dārta Pelse, & Ieva Raubiško. (2023). *The inclusion of migrants in policymaking. A report on Riga, Latvia.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941519>; Gunella, Chiara, & Orero, Pilar. (2023). *The inclusion of migrants in policy making. A report on Ripollet, Spain.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941549>; Desille Amandine, Tommasi Beatrice, & Montella Maria Grazia. (2023). *The inclusion of migrants in policy making. A report on the European Union.* Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7941646> (see version 2). To complete this information, we have conducted interviews with Agnese Lace, Providus (Latvia) on 16 March 2023; Marta Gili Lorente and Meritxell Caler Vergara, Municipality of Ripollet (Spain), on 17 March 2023; Julie Anne Wright, BCC (UK), on 3 April 2023. Feedbacks were also provided by MILE partners.

2) Mifriendly cities (na). Home. Available at: <https://mifriendlycities.co.uk/get-involved/citizens-voices/> [accessed on 23/05/23]

3) Birmingham city council (na). Foundation for Integration Project. Available at: https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/info/50227/city_of_sanctuary/2509/what_we_do_to_support_asylum_seekers_refugees_and_migrants/3 [accessed on 23/05/23].

The use of local and national funding is limited, with the exception of the current plurinstitutional Levelling up fund,⁴ set up to partly replace EU funds, within which the 12th and last mission encourages local leadership.⁵ In light of Brexit and the associated difficulties in securing European funding, Birmingham will need to capitalise on existing networks with other cities in order to remain involved in EU-funded projects as co-applicant.

Ioannina

The city showed a strong commitment to fostering political participation of migrants through **EU-funded projects and involvement in EU-wide networks**. After participating in two European consortia,⁶ Ioannina and a few other transnational partners participated in a new AMIF-funded project, ‘Empowering Migrants to Be Representative Actors in Community Engagement’ (EMBRACE).⁷ On the spur of these projects and networks, and thanks to a clear political commitment, the city has since 2021 established the **Migrant Integration Council within the city council**.

At the same time, the voluntary character of this advisory body and the lack of dedicated funding bring to question the body’s sustainability over the long term. Ioannina well exemplifies how progressive political orientations may contribute to an accommodative and inclusive integration policy, a greater local government’s embeddedness in multilevel governance relations, and a proactive engagement of civil society organisations (CSOs) and migrant organisations.⁸

The Ioannina case also shows that small- and medium-sized cities can develop **extensive policy networks both at local and European level**, and build on them **to secure further funding** and plan new activities.

In the examined cases, the EU therefore provides key funding opportunities to support projects and activities geared towards migrant political inclusion. However, as shown by the limited scope and range of activities, **the potential of EU resources remains underexploited**. The following section makes a case for their added value for municipalities in this policy field.

4) UK Government (2022), Levelling-up fund round 2: Prospectus, available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/levelling-up-fund-round-2-prospectus/levelling-up-fund-round-2-prospectus> [accessed on 24/04/2023].

5) Similar fund exists in the West Midlands Combined Authority, as it has been awarded 88 million pounds from the UK Shared Prosperity Fund (<https://www.wmca.org.uk/what-we-do/uk-shared-prosperity-fund/>). CSOs and municipalities alike must submit proposals, as this is not an automatic fund transfer. However, the priorities do not include political participation.

6) The ‘European Platform of Integrating Cities (EPIC)’ is a sharing network funded by AMIF between 2020 and 2022. Administered by the European Association of Local Democracy, it includes two regions and ten municipalities, among them Ioannina, and aims at gaining expertise in integration services (see <https://epicamif.eu/>). Political participation of migrant persons is not directly considered. The AMIF-funded ‘Raising Capacity for Inclusive People engaged in private sponsorship’ (RaCIP) running from 2020 to 2023 is mostly geared towards capacity-building for the creation of multi actors platform for the integration of refugees, based on the Portuguese experience.

7) EMBRACE (na), Goals and Activities, available at: <https://www.embrace-project.com/goals-and-activities/> [accessed on 24/04/2023].

8) These findings are in line with the results of the Whole-Comm Project, which explores the integration of post-2014 migrants in small and medium-sized towns and rural areas (SMsTRA). More information is available at <https://whole-comm.eu/>, and more specifically at <https://whole-comm.eu/working-papers/comparative-paper-on-local-integration-policies-and-multi-level-policy-making-interactions-in-smstra/>.

2 THE ADDED VALUE OF EU RESOURCES: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

1. Designing pilot projects

EU-funded projects can be designed as **pilot projects to implement activities that may not be funded otherwise**, for instance, due to possible reluctance of city councils and national governments to support them. Political inclusion of migrants, because of the varied sensitivities around migration, falls easily within this situation. Less costly and smaller than full-fledged programmes, pilot projects allow for the experimentation of innovative policies and integration approaches by reducing risks and costs (on innovative structures, see also [MILE policy brief 5](#)). Pilot projects moreover provide opportunities for capacity-building and knowledge production that may be used by policy makers for more long-lasting decisions and initiatives.⁹

In the four MILE municipalities, such projects have helped to **build trust with local organisations**, for example, through the funding of a community outreach coordinator role at the Birmingham City Council.¹⁰

They have contributed to **funding translation** of key documentation for newcomers, as it was done in Ioannina by the Intercultural Centre for Social Integration (Akadimia), financed by the Open Society Foundation.

They have been instrumental in **building migrant persons' and decision-makers' capacity**, such as the public leadership internship programme funded by the AMIF-funded '[EMBRACE](#)' project in Ioannina.

They have also been used to **create digital tools**: one example being the Migrant Advice Portal in Birmingham.¹¹ Something similar took place in Ioannina where, as part of the URBACT/Resilient Europe initiative, the municipality established Web platforms for consultations and 'Live Laboratories for Participant Planning'. Despite it being a crucial mechanism for residents' consultation, the platform was abandoned at the end of the project as it was deemed not user-friendly.

9) Slootjes J., Zanzuchi, M.B. (2023) "Toolkit for evidence-informed policymaking in migrant integration", available at: <https://www.migrationpolicy.org/sites/default/files/publications/spring-mpie-evidence-integration-policymaking-toolkit-final.pdf> [Accessed on 04/04/2023].

10) Between 2017 and 2020, the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) through the Urban Innovative Actions Initiative (UIA) awarded 4 million pounds to the MiFriendly Cities project, to enhance the contribution of migrants and refugees across the West Midlands region through an approach of active citizenship (see footnote 2 for the Website of the MiFriendly Cities). This enabled Birmingham City Council to fund two positions, including a 'Refugee and Migration Engagement Officer' to outreach to existing migrant-led organisations; but it also meant that the Council could support small-scale grassroots organisations already serving established ethnic minorities.

11) The on-going 'Foundation for Integration Project', an AMIF grant worth 2 million pounds, enables the funding of a position for the department of Prevention, Communities & Migration of the city council, support for local organisations - including the local Migrant and Refugee Centre - offering specialist advice for third-country nationals, and the set-up of the [Migrant Advice Portal](#).

Ensuring the sustainability of pilot projects is essential. It is therefore crucial to inbuild appropriate mechanisms from the start in order to change institutional and administrative practice in the long run, including:

- **Making project participation (and funding allocation) conditional upon policy change.** For example, in order to obtain the ‘MiFriendly City’ status under the EU-funded ‘MiFriendly Cities’ project, participating cities were obliged to involve migrant persons in the project’s development.
- **Providing a legally binding framework.** For instance, after having participated in the AMIF-funded project ‘IncluCities’, the Italian city of Capaci identified an advisory body to the local city council which would continue working on the activities established by the project. The commitment of the body to work on migrant political inclusion was enshrined in municipal policy via a formal act.¹²
- **Mainstreaming services and support for the inclusion of migrant persons.** As an example, Ripollet has adopted an intersectional approach in order to support different vulnerable social groups within and beyond the migrant community.

These long-term decisions can also keep cities engaged in European-wide networks and activities even when their political leadership changes and/or expresses less commitment.¹³

In addition, EU projects may potentially contribute to **changing the views of local governments** regarding the salience of certain issues, convincing them that more structural funding on their side needs to be allocated.

II. Building multi-stakeholder and migrant inclusive partnerships

EU-funded projects can be designed to **encourage the inclusion of various stakeholders as project partners.** The MILE project, for instance, provides the opportunity to involve migrant organisations as equal partners in developing project guidelines and objectives and in implementing activities. In this regard, CSOs, including migrant-serving ones, can play an important role. However, there are limitations to this approach. First of all, broad political outreach may prove difficult without the support of mediating structures run by members of migrant communities.¹⁴ Second, the persisting limited presence of migrant organisations as funding recipients and partners in migrant inclusion projects is in itself problematic.¹⁵

12) See *Inclucities (2023) Building a city for all*, available at: <https://inclucities.eu/media-events/resources>. The name of the legal act in Italian is “atto di giunta comunale”.

13) Fourot, Aude-Claire, Aisling Healy & Anouk Flamant (2022) *French participation in transnational migration networks: understanding city (dis)involvement and “passivism”*, *Local Government Studies*, 48:6, 1152–1174, DOI: 10.1080/03003930.2020.1857246.

14) de Graauw, Els (2015) “Polyglot Bureaucracies: Nonprofit Advocacy to Create Inclusive City Governments.” *Journal of Immigrant & Refugee Studies*, 13:2, 156–178.

15) Jenkins, Steve (2002) “Organising, Advocacy and Member Power.” *Working USA*, 6(2): 56–89.

16) Cappiali, Teresa (2016) “Whoever decides for you without you, s/he is against you!’: immigrant activism and the role of the Left in political racialization.” *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 40(6): 969–987.

III. Developing transnational networks and fostering social capital for the municipality

EU-funded projects also allow for the **inclusion of several stakeholders with different interests and ideologies**, e.g. trade unions, business associations and activist groups, across different municipalities and levels of government. This set-up reflects the reality that the governance of migration which requires the involvement of municipal, sub-national, national and European institutions, and that different localities often face comparable issues.¹⁷

EU-funded projects also encourage exchange and dialogue amongst different stakeholders to produce more effective policies. Indeed, while relations between those groups are often difficult in the local context, consortium participants may use project activities to **engage with different stakeholders from another city** to gain novel insights. Particularly after 2015, cities associated to promote a more accommodating agenda towards migrants in hostile national contexts.¹⁸

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THE EU PLAYS A KEY ROLE IN SUPPORTING NATIONAL GOVERNMENTS AND ALL OTHER INTEGRATION ACTORS THROUGH FUNDING, DEVELOPING PRACTICAL TOOLS, COORDINATING ACTIONS AND ESTABLISHING RELEVANT PARTNERSHIPS.
 ”
ACTION PLAN ON INTEGRATION AND INCLUSION (2021-2027),
 EUROPEAN COMMISSION

In the case of MILE’s partners, Birmingham has joined the City of Sanctuary Movement, whereas Riga has taken part in Eurocities and the Intercultural cities programme of the Council of Europe. Even if participation in those three networks does not involve direct funding, it might enhance access to further policy and funding opportunities, including participation in new EU-funded programmes.¹⁹

17) Zapata-Barrero, R., Caponio, T., & Scholten, P. (2017) *Theorising the ‘local turn in a multi-level governance framework of analysis: A case study in immigrant policies*. *International Review of Administrative Sciences*, 83(2), 241-246.

18) Oomen, B. (2020) *Decoupling and teaming up: The rise and proliferation of transnational municipal networks in the field of migration*. *International Migration Review*, 54(3), 913-939; Lacroix, T., and Spencer S. (2022) *City Networks and the Multi-Level Governance of Migration*. *Global Networks* 22, no 3: 349-62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/glob.12381>.

19) Lacroix and Desille (forthcoming) *International networking strategies of ordinary nodal cities: the case of Amadora in Portugal*, *Governance*.

3 IDENTIFYING EU RESOURCES TO SUPPORT THE POLITICAL INCLUSION OF MIGRANTS

Several EU funding instruments are available to municipalities to support multi-stakeholder consortia in the field of political inclusion. Some elements need to be considered.

The EU funding schemes create a complex chessboard of opportunities. The EU implements its programmes in three different ways: direct management, when the Commission manages the fund; indirect management, when Member States (MS)' authorities implement programmes under the Commissions' guidance; or shared management, when both MS and Commission co-manage the fund. Various entities can apply for EU funding, such as public bodies (whether local, regional or national), and non-governmental organisations (NGOs). At the beginning of every seven-year programming period, the Commission and EU MS agree on key priorities of funds whose management is shared. Once programmes are agreed, MS are tasked with their implementation and the Commission with monitoring and reimbursing expenditure.

” **EMPOWERING BOTH MIGRANTS AND HOST COMMUNITIES TO ACTIVELY ENGAGE IN THE INTEGRATION PROCESS IS ESSENTIAL TO ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE AND SUCCESSFUL INTEGRATION.** ”

ACTION PLAN ON INTEGRATION AND INCLUSION (2021-2027),
EUROPEAN COMMISSION

The **existing financial instruments** (see table 1 on page 9) may fund actions aimed at achieving the following goals:

- 1) enabling participation of the migrant population** in assemblies and parliaments;
- 2) extending voting rights** to settled third country nationals;
- 3) involving migrant residents in decision-making processes** at the local level and in the formulation of integration policies too;
- 4) supporting general civic and social engagement of migrant residents** in the voluntary sector, with the goal of facilitating interactions with the receiving society and fostering community-building activities.

In the Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021-2027), the Commission has recognised the **value of a multi-stakeholder approach**. It has encouraged MS and their funding authorities to use EU funding to involve in their programmes local and regional governments (LRGs), CSOs - including those representing migrants and diaspora communities - and social and economic partners. Moreover, the Commission has stressed the key role played by LRGs in engaging and consulting with the local communities to adjust national and regional integration and inclusion policies to local contexts and needs.

The role of local authorities has recently become even more prominent. Since June 2022, as a reaction to the fast increase in arrivals from Ukraine and the vocal requests of LRGs, the Commission adopted the “Flexible Assistance to Territories” (FAST-CARE). This allowed additional support and flexibility to Cohesion Policy funding, and most importantly, allocated 30% of such funding directly to local authorities and CSOs.²⁰

Useful **online resources** are available to guide municipalities in this field of EU funding:

- the “Toolkit on the use of EU funds for the integration of people with a migrant background,” created by the Commission;
- the European Website on Integration (EWSI), which devotes a web page on funding opportunities on migrant inclusion initiatives at EU and national levels;
- the European Commission’s official platform “Funding and Tenders”, where calls for proposals and projects are published;
- JASPERS, a technical assistance instrument set up by the Commission to help cities and regions attract and use European funds;
- Fi-compass, an EU platform offering advice on financial instruments and available funds.

Besides EU funds, several **transnational networks** – with different membership mechanisms – are an important resource for European LRGs. Some examples are Eurocities, the Council of European Municipalities and Regions (CEMR), the Assembly of European Regions (AER), and the European Association for Local Democracy (ALDA). Based in Brussels and regularly consulted at the various stages of EU policy-making, these networks lobby at the European level. They also represent an opportunity for cities and regions to interact with the European institutions as well as giving European institutions the means to implement some of their integration policy programmes and²¹ to keep abreast of the needs at the local level. More information on multi-stakeholders’ networks at the subnational level can be found in our policy paper 1 on migrant inclusion in decision making and the role of local governments.

20) European Commission (2022) “Flexible Assistance to Territories (FAST-CARE)”, available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/publications/communications/2022/flexible-assistance-to-territories-fast-care_en.

21) Whole-Comm Project explores the integration of post-2014 migrants in small and medium-sized towns and rural areas (SMsTRA). More information is available at <https://whole-comm.eu/>, and more specifically at <https://whole-comm.eu/working-papers/comparative-paper-on-local-integration-policies-and-multi-level-policy-making-interactions-in-smstra/>.

Table 1. EU funding schemes

	What are the main objectives and actions funded?	Which actors have access to funds?	How are funds managed? Do municipalities have direct access?
Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) ²²	The reception phase of the integration of TCNs. The promotion of dialogue between TCNs, receiving societies, and public authorities.	State and federal authorities, local public bodies, NGOs, private actors, research organisations. Multi-stakeholder partnerships are encouraged.	Yes, but only for the part directly managed by the Commission. It funds transnational projects on integration and cooperates with public and private partners, such as LRGs, CSOs, NGOs.
European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) ²³	Socio-economic inclusion in labour market and education of TCNs and marginalised communities.	Multi-stakeholder partnerships are strongly encouraged, also through its Transnational Cooperation Platform.	MS and regions are the main actors responsible for its implementation. Municipalities do not have direct access to it.
European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) ²⁴	Socio-economic inclusion of immigrant people and/or people with a migrant background. Education, employment, housing, social care, regeneration of deprived urban and rural areas.	Public and private bodies in all EU regions.	It co-funds some initiatives to whom municipalities may have direct access: the European Urban Initiative (EUI), and URBACT projects (aimed to form networks between European cities)
Erasmus + ²⁵	Initiatives to promote tolerance and respond to the needs of migrant children and young people.	It promotes partnerships for cooperation and exchange of best practices. Individuals and organisations are the main beneficiaries.	Managed both by National Agencies and by EACEA. LRGs have access to it.
Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values (CERV) ²⁶	It supports democratic, equal, open and inclusive societies, including citizens’ engagement and participation.	Civil society organisations, among others.	Managed by EACEA, LRGs have access to it.

22) European Union (2021) REGULATION (EU) 2021/1147 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 7 July 2021 establishing the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund. The last AMIF call (January 2023) is available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/amif/wp-call/2023/call-fiche_amif-2022-tf2-ag_en.pdf.

23) European Commission (2023) European Social Fund Plus, available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/european-social-fund-plus/en> [accessed in 04/2023]. On individual country cases, one can check: <https://ec.europa.eu/european-social-fund-plus/en/support-your-country> [accessed in 04/2023]. See also the Transnational Cooperation Platform: <https://ec.europa.eu/european-social-fund-plus/en/transnational-cooperation-platform> [accessed in 04/2023].

24) European Commission (2023) European Regional Development Fund, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en [accessed in 04/2023]; European Urban Initiative (2023) The Initiative, available at <https://www.urban-initiative.eu/> [accessed in 04/2023]; URBACT (2023), home, available at: <https://urbact.eu> [accessed in 04/2023].

25) European commission (2023) Erasmus plus, available at: <https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/projects/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-of-life> [accessed in 04/2023].

26) European Commission (2023) Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values programme, available at: https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/justice-and-consumers/justice-and-consumers-funding-tenders/funding-programmes/citizens-equality-rights-and-values-programme_en [accessed in 04/2023].

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This policy brief is primarily addressed to European municipalities working on migrant political inclusion. **It encourages towns and cities** of all sizes with a sizable migrant population **to engage in more EU-level projects and activities** to stimulate political inclusion as a necessary step towards political participation, particularly by involving migrant-led as well as other types of stakeholders. Under the right conditions, those activities are likely not only to lead to better dialogue and exchange with migrant communities, but also to provide access to social and economic opportunities that will enhance the political and economic standing of the municipality in the medium- to long-term.

On this basis, for projects on migrant political (and social) inclusion, we provide several recommendations for municipalities below.

For municipalities never involved in EU-funded projects or EU-wide networks:

- **reach out to other EU municipalities to discuss potential collaboration** and participation in a consortium funded under the EU programs listed above;
- **participate in EU-wide networks of cities and towns** as a way to become aware of new opportunities in the field and develop useful contacts for future consortium-building;

For municipalities with experience of EU-funded projects and EU-wide networks

- **involve migrant organisations and migrant individuals from the start** in the conceptualisation of project objectives, activities and deliverables to ensure responsiveness to the needs of migrant communities, and include activities that relate to training or other capacity-building measures which may help migrant organisations build expertise and knowledge, professionalise or grow in a sustainable manner;
- **involve a variety of stakeholders** with different interests and ideological perspectives around migration and migrant inclusion (e.g. trade unions, civil society organisations, employer associations, religious organisations);
- **build on existing EU-wide and global networks of cities** to draw from examples of good practices in promoting and supporting migrants' political inclusion.

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WWW.MILE-PROJECT.EU

Contact: Vanessa Cotterell, v.cotterell@unitee.eu

The MILE project is co-funded by the European Union.

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